

Notes

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with Heterocyclic Bases and Homophthalic Acid and Tetrachlorophthalic Acid

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THE mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) with homophthalic (H_2PA) and tetrachlorophthalic acids (H_2TCPA) as primary ligands and quinoline (Q), isoquinoline (IQ), pyridine (Py), 2-aminopyridine (APy), 2-picoline (Pic), *o*-phenanthroline (Phen) and dipyriddy (Dipy) as secondary ligands were prepared and characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, conductance, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral studies. The dipyriddy and *o*-phenanthroline complexes of cobalt(II) were tetrahedral and of nickel(II) were square-planar in the case of homophthalic acid only while all other complexes were of octahedral structure.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. The solvents were distilled before use.

Preparation of complexes: Ethanolic solutions (50.0 ml) containing metal chlorides (0.05 M) and the ligands H_2PA and H_2TCPA (0.05 M each) were mixed with 0.05 M ethanolic solution (100.0 ml) of potassium hydroxide. The white crystalline precipitates of potassium chloride formed were filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated to about 100.0 ml. A little more than 50.0 ml ethanolic solution of 0.05 M heterocyclic bases were then added. The mixtures were allowed to cool in an ice-bath for 24 h. The precipitates formed were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, washed with carbon tetrachloride and air-dried.

Physicochemical measurements: Infrared spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer using thin film technique at slow scanning. The electronic spectra were run on a Carl-Zeiss SPECORD uv-vis spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were carried out on a Princeton Applied Research 155 digital vibrating sample magnetometer with an attachment of EG and G, PARC 152 cryogenic temperature controller under a magnetic field of 5000 gauss produced by a Polytronic Electromagnet H. E. M. 200. Conductivity measurements were carried out on a Systronic 302 conductivity bridge.

The results of elemental analysis, m.p., and the values of molar conductances of cobalt(II) com-

plexes in acetone and of nickel(II) complexes in dimethylformamide are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	M.p. °C	Analysis % :		Λ_m $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		Found	(Calcd.)	
[Co(PA)(IQ) ₂]	160	7.83 (7.93)	7.44 (7.50)	3.09
[Co(PA)(APy) ₂]	260d	13.87 (13.60)	13.18 (13.81)	5.75
[Co(PA)(Q) ₂]	200d	7.83 (7.01)	7.44 (6.83)	2.40
[Co(PA)(Py) ₂]	140	10.66 (10.50)	10.13 (9.65)	10.96
[Co(PA)(Pic) ₂]	200d	9.68 (9.38)	9.20 (9.12)	5.05
[Co(TCPA)(IQ) ₂]	125	6.72 (6.47)	6.39 (6.34)	2.45
[Co(TCPA)(APy) ₂]	220d	10.74 (10.63)	10.20 (10.06)	0.26
[Co(TCPA)(Pic) ₂]	240d	8.04 (7.87)	7.64 (7.37)	5.36
[Co(TCPA)(Py) ₂]	260	8.71 (8.69)	8.27 (7.31)	3.03
[Co(TCPA)(Q) ₂]	232	6.72 (6.44)	6.39 (6.47)	2.30
[Co(PA)(Phen)]	275d	14.13 (13.87)	6.72 (7.04)	3.45
[Co(PA)(Dipy)]	220	15.00 (14.86)	7.13 (7.78)	3.03
[Co(TCPA)(Phen)]	245	10.89 (11.03)	5.18 (5.23)	0.32
[Co(TCPA)(Dipy)]	225	11.40 (11.20)	5.82 (4.87)	0.28
[Ni(PA)(IQ) ₂]	240d	7.80 (7.04)	7.44 (6.93)	22.23
[Ni(PA)(APy) ₂]	240d	13.82 (13.29)	13.19 (14.04)	18.66
[Ni(PA)(Phen)]	178	14.09 (13.53)	6.72 (6.39)	25.37
[Ni(PA)(Py) ₂]	235d	10.62 (10.35)	10.13 (10.31)	23.01
[Ni(PA)(Dipy)]	150	14.95 (14.69)	7.13 (7.35)	11.16
[Ni(PA)(Pic) ₂]	210d	8.64 (8.97)	9.20 (8.88)	28.00
[Ni(PA)(Q) ₂]	240d	7.80 (7.40)	7.44 (7.52)	24.25
[Ni(TCPA)(IQ) ₂]	205d	6.70 (6.05)	6.39 (6.36)	25.00
[Ni(TCPA)(APy) ₂]	225d	10.70 (10.23)	10.21 (10.64)	20.75
[Ni(TCPA)(Py) ₂]	245d	8.68 (7.99)	8.28 (7.89)	0.45
[Ni(TCPA)(Phen) ₂]	220d	8.15 (7.89)	7.77 (7.07)	23.28
[Ni(TCPA)(Dipy) ₂]	210d	8.73 (8.16)	8.32 (8.12)	31.00
[Ni(TCPA)(Pic) ₂]	242d	8.01 (7.78)	7.64 (7.44)	19.29
[Ni(TCPA)(Q) ₂]	240d	6.70 (6.75)	6.39 (6.59)	0.49

*PA²⁻ = C₈H₆O₄²⁻, TCPA²⁻ = C₈O₄Cl₂²⁻, IQ = C₉H₇N,
APy = C₇H₆N₂, Q = C₈H₇N, Py = C₅H₅N,
Pic = C₈H₇N, Dipy = C₁₀H₈N₂, Phen = C₁₂H₈N₂.

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Results and Discussion

The strong ir bands at 1 700 and 1 440 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{C-O} in the spectra of homophthalic acid were shifted to $\approx 1 600$ and $\approx 1 400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of cobalt(II) complexes and to 1 580 and 1 400 cm^{-1} in the spectra of nickel(II) complexes, respectively. Similarly, the strong bands at 1 650 and 1 400 cm^{-1} in the case of tetrachlorophthalic acid were shifted to 1 600 and 1 350 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the complexes of both the metal ions. This indicated the coordination of these acids through carboxyl groups. The characteristic ring vibrations of the heterocyclic bases in the range 1 600–1 450 cm^{-1} generally show significant changes on complexation as reported by Das and Rao¹ in their studies on Mn^{2+} complexes of pyridine *etc.*, but in our case, these bands could not be distinguished perhaps because of overlapping or mixing with $\nu_{C=O}$ stretching bands. The in-plane ring deformation mode observed at $\approx 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ undergoes a positive shift in the mixed ligand complexes confirming thereby a coordination through nitrogen. Paul *et al.*² also reported the same type of observations in their complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline.

The μ_{eff} values for complexes of cobalt(II) except those with *o*-phenanthroline and dipyriddy were 5.0 B.M. indicating their high-spin octahedral structure. Their electronic spectra in acetone gave two bands in the region 15 000–16 000 (ν_2) and at 18 000 cm^{-1} (ν_3) corresponding to the transitions, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, respectively. The transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) could not be observed due to the limited spectral range of the instrument and hence these were calculated using band fitting procedure³ and found to be $\approx 7 400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The μ_{eff} values of the *o*-phenanthroline and dipyriddy complexes were found to be ~ 4.5 B.M. indicating their tetrahedral structure. Their electronic spectra gave two intense bands at $\approx 15 000$ and $\approx 24 000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to transitions ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) and charge transfer, respectively. The intensity (ϵ) values of ≈ 420 for ν_3 also confirmed their tetrahedral structure, the value for octahedral complexes were found to be ~ 5 only. The variations in the values of μ_{eff} and of molar susceptibilities χ_M with temperature also indicated their octahedral geometry. The μ_{eff} and χ_M values of *o*-phenanthroline and dipyriddy complexes were almost independent of temperature indicating their tetrahedral structure⁴.

Nickel(II) complexes of homophthalic acid except with dipyriddy and *o*-phenanthroline gave three bands in the range 9 000–12 000, 14 000–19 000 and 26 000–30 000 cm^{-1} corresponding to transitions, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. The values of B (Racah parameter) were calculated using the diagonal sum rule⁵ and were found in the range 800–1 000 cm^{-1} . The calculated

energies of ν_2 and ν_3 were in good agreement with the observed values indicating their octahedral structure. The μ_{eff} values were 2.91–3.78 B.M. The near independence of μ_{eff} values with temperature also confirmed A_1 ground term, and hence the octahedral geometry⁶. Nickel homophthalate complexes of dipyriddy and *o*-phenanthroline were diamagnetic and their electronic spectra in methanol gave three charge transfer bands at $\approx 41 000$, $\approx 33 500$ and $32 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to the transitions, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_u$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2u}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1u}$, respectively, indicating their square-planar structure. Their metal d-orbital energies were calculated assuming $F_2 = 10F_4 = 700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The values of Δ_2 and Δ_3 were found to be 8 300 and 5 750 cm^{-1} for dipyriddy complexes and 8 100 and 6 150 cm^{-1} for *o*-phenanthroline complexes, respectively.

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Synthesis and Characterisation of Lanthanide Iodide and Thiocyanate Complexes with 5,6-Benzoquinoline-*N*-oxide

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A number of workers¹⁻³ have isolated a number of lanthanide(III) complexes of aromatic amine-*N*-oxides and found that these ligands occupied six to ten coordination positions of the lanthanide ion. To confirm the view we have isolated a number of complexes of lanthanide iodides and thiocyanates with 5,6-benzoquinoline-*N*-oxide (hereafter Benzquo).

Experimental

5,6-Benzoquinoline was obtained from E. Merck and its *N*-oxidation was carried out by method of Ochiai⁴.

$[\text{Ln}(\text{Benzquo})_3(\text{NCS})_3]$: A warm ethanolic solution (20 ml) of lanthanide nitrate hexahydrate (1.0 mmol) was added to warm ethanolic solution (40 ml)